

Table S2. Summary of acoustic recordings at offshore structures in the Mid-Atlantic and Gulf of Maine (Peterson et al. 2014; Peterson et al. 2016).

Map ID	Site	Structure	Coordinates	Height (m)	Distance from land (km)	Water depth (m)	Year	Survey dates	Nights	Total passes	Maximum passes	Overall rate ^a	Peak hour after sunset	Peak month	Species diversity
<i>Mid-Atlantic</i>															
A	Albermarle ATON, NC	Beacon	36.04506, -76.0014	3	7.9	6	2012	06/20-12/31	195	647	67	3.32	3	9	4
							2013	01/01-08/02	183	51	24	0.28	4	7	3
							2014	02/28-12/31	137	279	33	2.04	3	10	6
B	Chesapeake Light Tower, VA	Tower	36.90972, -75.7097	36	24.8	12	2012	04/29-10/25	180	165	144	0.92	6	5	1
							2013	01/01-12/31	365	71	13	0.19	6	9	3
							2014	01/01-11/30	326	103	42	0.32	1	8	4
C	Chesapeake Bay Bridge Tunnel, VA	Building	37.036669, -76.076649	15	12.1	12	2012	04/26-11/26	215	3115	234	14.49	3	7	4
							2013	05/17-12/18	216	1777	133	8.23	3	9	3
							2014	03/01-12/15	290	1474	84	5.08	3	8	3
<i>Gulf of Maine</i>															
D	NERACOOS Buoy I, ME	Buoy	44.1, -68.1	2	26.2	101	2013	06/24-12/31	191	9	3	0.05	1	8	1
							2014	01/01-03/03	62	0	0	0.00			
E	NERACOOS Buoy F, ME	Buoy	44.05, -68.99	2	5.9	55	2013	06/17-09/24	100	233	22	2.33	3	8	5
F	NERACOOS Buoy E, ME	Buoy	43.71, -69.35	2	18.8	93	2012	04/11-12/31	265	378	44	1.43	2	8	3
G	NERACOOS Buoy B, ME	Buoy	43.17, -70.42	2	14.1	63	2012	04/11-12/31	265	411	32	1.55	2	8	3
							2013	01/01-12/17	203	93	11	0.46	2	8	3
H	NERACOOS Buoy A, MA	Buoy	42.52, -70.56	2	10.5	64	2011	06/01-10/15	137	84	9	0.61	2	8	3
							2012	04/14-07/02	80	7	3	0.09	1	5	2
							2013	06/18-08/18	62	41	20	0.66	2	7	3
							2014	04/01-04/17	17	0	0	0.00			
I	Matinicus Rock, ME	Lighthouse	43.783831, -68.855002	14	32.9	34	2009	09/02-09/14	13	102	43	7.85	1		4
							2010	08/05-10/31	88	178	24	2.02	8	8	3
							2012	06/22-10/23	124	1495	326	12.06	2	10	4
							2013	06/25-11/04	133	441	161	3.32	2	9	4
							2014	04/04-12/31	272	111	21	0.41	1	8	4
J	Mount Desert Rock, ME	Lighthouse	43.964338, -68.1411	17	41.6	68	2009	08/17-12/31	137	597	168	4.36	1	8	4
							2010	08/26-12/31	128	277	92	2.16	2	9	3
							2011	01/01-09/17	260	366	133	1.41	1	8	4
							2013	07/09-07/23	15	7	7	0.47	1		1
							2014	08/08-10/27	81	336	77	4.15	1	8	3
K	Halfway Rock, ME	Lighthouse	43.655994, -70.0369	23	8.3	20	2009	08/13-12/31	141	287	60	2.04	3	8	4
							2010	01/01-02/24	55	0	0	0.00			
							2013	05/31-07/01	32	3	1	0.09			1

^a passes/detector-night